

1 **Current methods for the evaluation of chemical contamination**
2 **risks from abandoned coal and lead-zinc mine lands: Protocol for**
3 **a systematic evidence map**

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29 **ABSTRACT**

30 **Background:** Abandoned mine lands (AMLs) pose significant environmental risks by releasing
31 contaminants that can adversely affect plants, animals, and human health, especially in highly
32 contaminated areas. Guidance exists on conducting contaminated land risk assessments. Understanding
33 and documenting changes in the methods used for AMLs risk assessments can help identify gaps and
34 advances in practice, influencing future research, policy, and remediation efforts.

35 **Methods:** The study aims to synthesise current methods for characterising the risks of chemical
36 contamination associated with AMLs, with a focus on coal and lead-zinc mines due to their enduring
37 toxic legacies.

38 **Search Strategy:** Searches will be conducted across six electronic databases, including Web of
39 Science, Scopus, ScienceDirect, PubMed, Academic Search Complete, and Business Source Premier
40 (via EbscoHost), as well as grey literature sources.

41 **Eligibility Criteria:** Eligible studies must include primary research assessing chemical risks from
42 abandoned coal and lead-zinc mines. They must have assessed or measured risks associated with
43 chemicals on ecological or human receptors at the community, population, or individual level.

44 **Screening & Data Extraction:** Studies retrieved from literature searches will undergo title and abstract
45 screening, followed by a full-text assessment for eligibility. Following pilot screening, a single reviewer
46 will screen ~~the titles and abstracts of~~ all articles independently, with a second reviewer verifying
47 accuracy for 20% of the sources. ~~Data~~[A data extraction will be extracted from eligible](#)~~undertaken for~~
48 ~~the included studies using a piloted data from full text screening.~~[Data on methods for exposure](#)
49 [assessment, including exposure modelling where relevant, selected safety thresholds, risk](#)
50 [characterisation, including safety threshold,](#) will be extracted from all eligible studies. [Accuracy of the](#)
51 [extraction process will also be verified by a second reviewer for 20% of the eligible articles.](#)

52 **Study Analysis & Reporting:** ~~Collated m~~[Methods](#) will be ~~categorised~~~~lated~~ to establish current
53 practices and compared with existing guidance to assess alignment and deviations. Results will be
54 summarised narratively and presented in interactive, publicly accessible visualisations.

55

56 **Keywords:** Abandoned mine lands, contaminants, risk assessment, toxicity.

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60 [Authors' contributions:](#)

61 Joanne McPhie: Methodology and Resources. Olwenn V. Martin: Conceptualisation, Data curation, Funding
62 acquisition, Methodology, Project administration, Software, Supervision, Validation, and Writing - review &
63 editing. Rakesh Kanda: Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision, Validation, and Writing - review
64 & editing. Trevor Hoey: Writing - review & editing. Ushemegbe R. Ekharefo: Conceptualisation, Data curation,
65 Funding acquisition, Methodology, Validation, Writing - original draft, and Writing - review & editing.

66 This systematic evidence map was conceptualised by URE under the supervision of OVM. URE contributed her
67 expertise in environmental geology and chemical contamination, OVM in environmental sciences, toxicology,

68 chemical risk assessment and systematic evidence maps. RK lent his knowledge in analytical chemistry, and TH
69 offered expertise in contaminant dispersal in rivers through sediment transport and consequent environmental
70 impacts. JMP provided expertise in information systems. The search strategy was developed by URE, with input
71 and discussions from OVM and JMP. Eligibility criteria were developed by URE and OVM and piloted by URE,
72 OVM and RK. The draft data extraction template was prepared by URE, revised following inputs from OVM and
73 was piloted by URE and OVM. URE prepared the final draft of the protocol. All co-authors reviewed successive
74 versions of the protocol.

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76

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82 Competing Interests

83 Authors have no competing interests. Complete declarations of interest for all co-authors are provided.

84 Data availability statement

85 Supplementary materials relating to this protocol can be found here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14246187>

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90 Background

91 Historically, the mining of natural resources did not always adequately consider impacts on health and
92 the environment (Gallart, 2017; Macklin et al., 2023). Mining activities vary greatly in method and
93 scale, including artisanal and industrial mining at small, medium, or larger scales, and open-pit, surface,
94 and underground methods. Many past mining operations lacked planning and were conducted
95 haphazardly, leaving behind a legacy of contaminated mine lands (Hasheela et al., 2015). Mine closure,
96 the planned or unplanned cessation of a mining operation, is a critical phase in the mining life cycle that
97 ought to be designed and included in the mine operation plan (De Graff, 2020). Properly designed
98 closure aims to restore land for ecological or alternative uses, ensure ecological and human safety, and
99 reduce environmental and social damage (De Graff, 2020; ICMM, 2019, 2021; Laurence, 2006). The
100 costs of mine closure are significant and, as a result, mine lands are often left unattended when mineral
101 resources are exhausted (ICMM, 2019, 2021). An abandoned mine refers to a former mine where
102 extraction and processing occurred that is no longer in operation and for which there is no responsible
103 entity to finance the cost of remediation or restoration. By contrast, abandoned mine lands (AMLs)
104 ~~encompass include lands including~~ waste repository sites, water bodies, and surrounding watersheds
105 where extraction, beneficiation, or processing of mineral resources has occurred. ~~AMLs and~~ are also
106 defined by the absence of responsible parties to oversee their management or restoration (EA, 2008;
107 Holmes & Stewart, 2011; US EPA, 2024). The difference is in their scope and structure, both
108 characterised by a range of landscape features that may include stagnant pond water, mine water, waste

109 rocks, tailings impoundments, areas impacted by smelter plumes, abandoned equipment₁ and structures.
 110 Many mining companies ceased operations before environmental regulations governing the
 111 management of mines came into force in their respective jurisdiction. Hence, governments are often
 112 left with the legacies of abandoned mines and responsibility for their rehabilitation (Coelho et al., 2011;
 113 Hasheela et al., 2015). Globally, over a million abandoned mines (Figure 1) have been identified,
 114 including shafts, adits, and alluvial surface mines (Coelho et al., 2011).

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Figure 1: Estimated number of AMLs in some regions and countries 1. (BML, 2017); 2. (Ashby & van-Etten, 2021); 3. (EEA, 2004); 4. (Hughes, 2024a); 5. (Martínez-López et al., 2021); 6. (Tyson, 2020); 7. (Hans, 2021); 8. (MECD, 2022); 9. (Venkateswarlu et al., 2016)

122 Abandoned mines are significant sources of persistent contamination, primarily due to heavy metals,
123 polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), and natural radionuclides (Gopinathan et al., 2023). These
124 pollutants are released through mine waste, tailings, acid mine drainage (AMD), and other
125 environmental processes (Iatan, 2021). Heavy metals such as arsenic, lead, cadmium, and chromium
126 persist in these sites, accumulating in waste and tailings, with increased mobility ~~under~~ acidic
127 conditions (Han et al., 2023; Wolkersdorfer & Mugova, 2022). PAHs are carcinogenic and mutagenic,
128 partially persistent in anaerobic or low oxygen conditions, and bind strongly ~~to~~ sediments and soil
129 (Bukowska et al., 2022; Li et al., 2019; Venkatraman et al., 2024). Natural radionuclides, including
130 uranium, thorium, and radon, pose radiotoxic risks through inhalation or ingestion, depending on the
131 environmental conditions (Momčilović et al., 2013; Paul et al., 2022). These contaminants migrate
132 through soil, water, and air, influencing surrounding ecosystems and necessitating detailed
133 environmental and health assessments to guide remediation efforts.

134 AMD is a major source of contamination, affecting watercourses globally. Many specific sites have
135 been described in the literature (e.g., Tinto-Odiel rivers in southern Spain (Grande et al., 2003), surface
136 waters of Gujiao and Gyama valley in ~~China~~ China (Huang et al., 2010; Ping et al., 2017), and Blyde
137 river catchment in South Africa (Selebalo et al., 2021). Over 23,000 km of contaminated rivers have
138 been recorded in the United States (Cravotta et al., 2010; Gammons et al., 2010).⁷ Additionally, the
139 release of heavy metals and PAHs into surrounding soils and sediments can cause extensive pollution,
140 with high contamination levels recorded in rivers and soils (Han et al., 2023; Hughes, 2024a; Sartorius,
141 2024; Wolkersdorfer & Mugova, 2022). In coal AMLs, PAHs contribute to environmental and health
142 risks, with severe implications for aquatic ecosystems (Li et al., 2019). Moreover, the dispersion of
143 pollutants through surface runoff, groundwater leaching, and sediment transport exacerbates the
144 contamination of water and soil resources (Candeias et al., 2015; Patel et al., 2024).

145
146 The persistence of pollutants such as heavy metals and organic contaminants in the environment poses
147 ongoing risks to both ~~humans~~ human and ecosystems (Sartorius, 2023), especially when combined,
148 leading to the loss of plant and animal species (Coelho et al., 2011; Venkateswarlu et al., 2016;
149 Worlanyo & Jiangfeng, 2021). Studies of abandoned lead-zinc mines reveal their long-term health
150 effects (Chukwu & Obiora, 2023; Obiora et al., 2016; Sartorius et al., 2022; Son et al., 2019; US EPA,
151 2000b), highlighting the need for targeted remediation and risk management (Naidu et al., 2019;
152 Rouhani et al., 2023).

153
154 Assessing these risks is critical to preventing long-term environmental damage and protecting public
155 health. Risk ~~can be defined as the product of~~ the impact ~~multiplied by and~~ the probability of that event
156 occurring. In this context, risk is the potential for harmful impacts resulting from exposure to
157 environmental stressors that could be physical, geological, biological, or chemical entities (Bartell,

158 2008; US EPA, 1998). Chemical risk assessment (CRA) typically consists of the comparison of an
159 exposure level, the concentration of the chemical of interest in a given compartment (exposure
160 assessment), with the corresponding safety threshold, derived from knowledge of the toxicity of that
161 chemical (hazard assessment). In developing CRA methods for AMLs, most attention is paid to
162 characterising exposures whilst the risk characterisation typically makes use of existing regulatory
163 safety thresholds. Consequently, AMLs chemical risk assessment (CRA for AMLs essentially aligns
164 with frameworks used in contaminated land assessment and follows a structured four-step evaluation
165 involving hazard identification, hazard assessment, exposure assessment, and risk characterisation
166 (ISO, 2017; OECD, 2021; UK EA, 2020; US EPA, 2022; WHO, 2010). Whilst they may vary according
167 contextual environmental factors, the hazardous properties of a chemical, such as mobility, toxicity,
168 persistence, and bioaccumulation are intrinsic to a substance's chemical structure and physico-chemical
169 properties and independent of specific sites, and so are considered consistent and measurable across
170 contexts. CRA in AMLs typically use existing safety thresholdthreshold from regulatory hazard
171 evaluation. Whilst a reference for that safety threshold is given, the process to select it is rarely reported.
172 Accordingly, for this systematic evidence map, we will capture the sources of the hazard thresholds
173 and, when available, the process and rationale for their selection. As a result, CRA in AMLs) typically
174 begins with site characterisation, involving a desk study to review historical data, including Earth
175 Observation data, and a walkover survey to develop an initial Conceptual Site Model (CSM). This
176 model identifies potential contaminant sources, exposure pathways, and receptors at risk. This
177 informsmay be followed by field the sampling strategy, sample preparation, and laboratory analysis to
178 identify and quantify contaminants in line with established standards and procedures (ISO, 2018; UK
179 EA, 2020; US EPA, 2000a).

180
181 ~~Accordingly, for this systematic evidence map, we will capture the sources of the and references~~
182 ~~for the hazard thresholds and, when available, the process and rationale for their selection theseand~~
183 ~~characterisation used in included studies rather than attempting to document or retrieve detailed~~
184 ~~information about hazard evaluation of individual substances. Conversely, exposure assessment~~
185 ~~methods specific to the AML context, and we We aim to capture exposure assessment methods specific~~
186 ~~to the AML contextthese specificities. Risk characterisation is conducted by comparing estimated~~
187 ~~exposure levels with toxicological thresholds, such as the Reference Dose (RfD) or Acceptable Daily~~
188 ~~Intake (ADI) to determine whether there is a significant risk (ISO, 2017; OECD, 2021; UK EA, 2020;~~
189 ~~US EPA, 2022; WHO, 2010). Risk characterisation of AMLs is necessary to evaluate individual sites,~~
190 ~~prioritise those requiring remediation, and develop sustainable, site-specific mitigation plans to protect~~
191 ~~affected receptors. The outcome of CRAs informs mitigation strategies such as site remediation. This~~
192 ~~risk management, the final stage of risk assessment, which is not consideredis beyond the scope of in~~
193 ~~this systematic evidence map (SEM). Risk characterisation of AMLs is necessary to evaluate individual~~

194 ~~sites, prioritise those requiring remediation, and develop sustainable, site-specific mitigation plans to~~
195 ~~protect affected receptors. The effectiveness of these outcomes depends mainly on the approach or~~
196 ~~method employed, making method selection a critical step in the risk assessment process.~~

198 1.1 Rationale

199 This ~~evidence map~~ aims to identify and synthesise methods used to assess and evaluate chemical risks
200 from AMLs. This study seeks to ~~establish-identify~~ current practices, ~~if any, as~~ reported in ~~the~~ peer-
201 reviewed literature ~~if any~~. Although many national and international guidelines are available (e.g.
202 ~~CCME, 2016; ICMM, 2007, 2016; ISO, 2017; NEPM, 2014; UK EA, 2020; US EPA, 2000a; WHO,~~
203 ~~2010), most are general (for contaminated lands overall) and not tailored to AML-specific complexities.~~
204 In contrast, academic research frequently applies more tailored and nuanced, site-specific assessments.

205 AMLs present unique challenges ~~compared to typical contaminated land (CL)~~ due to their diverse
206 contaminant sources, multiple pathways, diffuse pollution, and persistent environmental legacies. The
207 complex interactions of physical, chemical, and environmental hazards (BML, 2017; DEP, 2015;
208 Fields, 2003; Lottermoser, 2010; Venkateswarlu et al., 2016) are associated with the nature of mining
209 operations, the type of mine structures, and long-term legacy impacts (Hufty, 2019; Jain et al., 2016),
210 which amplify overall risk. ~~Consequently, the method of risk assessments (RA) of AMLs goes beyond~~
211 ~~a narrow focus on soil or water contamination typical of CL scenarios.~~ As recognised by ICMM (2007),
212 traditional RA and guidance fail to consider the specificities of metals, a major problem in AMLs
213 (ICMM, 2007). They require additional layers of considerations, such as mine infrastructure, waste
214 repositories, geotechnical instability of hillslopes and tailings dams, river mobility, and the chronic
215 effects of AMD. ~~Futhermore~~ ~~More so~~ ~~Consequently~~, the scope of contaminants studied, the sampling
216 strategies, analytical methods, exposure models, specific sources, multiple pathways, contaminant fate
217 and transport models, and specific receptors typically considered in ~~CRAs of AMLs~~ ~~RA context, which~~
218 may ~~differ~~ ~~have been omitted~~ from ~~some established~~ guidance that applies to contaminated land more
219 generally.

220 ~~A recent systematic methodology for hazard assessment in AMLs integrates multi-hazard interactions,~~
221 ~~incorporating tools such as interaction matrices, hazard diagrams, and multi-hazard indices (Al Heib &~~
222 ~~Franck, 2024). The approach assessed the level, intensity, probability, temporality, and significance of~~
223 ~~hazard interactions to support more robust risk quantification and decision making. The case~~
224 ~~application at an abandoned coal mine demonstrated both the complexity of such environments and the~~
225 ~~value of integrated, expert-driven assessment for effective mitigation (Al Heib et al., 2023; Al Heib &~~
226 ~~Franck, 2024). These new considerations are AML-specific which that do not reflect in general CL~~
227 ~~guidance.~~

228 Furthermore, ~~CRA risk assessment~~ methods for AMLs need to be able to cope with increased
229 complexity resulting from climate change and increased anthropogenic pressures. Accounting for
230 multiple ~~chemical stressors hazards~~, mixture risk assessment, and considering the effects of changing
231 magnitude and/or frequency of extreme events, sea-level rise, and other consequences of climate
232 change, is required as these factors may modify exposure and therefore risks (Marras et al., 2022). For
233 instance, extreme rainfall and rising temperatures can accelerate AMD formation, enhance contaminant
234 mobility, and widen pollutant dispersion (Anawar, 2013; Jacqueline et al., 2021; Li et al., 2024).
235 Additionally, climate-driven impacts, including erosion, permafrost thaw, altered hydrology, and land
236 instability (Bulovic et al., 2024; Palma et al., 2019; Santos et al., 2019), threaten ecosystems and human
237 health (Grajal-Puche et al., 2024; Hughes, 2024a). A case from Kam Kotia AML in Canada highlights
238 ~~how that~~ in 2012, rapid snowmelt caused a tailings dam breach, releasing contaminated water and
239 sediment into the surrounding environment (MacMillan et al., 2021).

240 ~~Fate models (computational tools that simulate how pollutants move and transform in the environment),
241 are increasingly applied in AML contexts to predict the long term behaviour of contaminants, especially
242 metals, and their movement through environmental media. These tools are vital for understanding
243 potential risks to human health and the environment, and they are crucial for developing effective
244 remediation and restoration strategies (Ettler et al., 2025; Marras et al., 2022).~~ Some regulatory updates
245 now reflect these emerging concerns. For example, the UK's updated guidance (UK EA, 2020)
246 mandates that climate change impacts be considered from project inception through long-term
247 monitoring of contaminated land.

248 A bibliographic search for literature reviews synthesising methods of risk assessment specific to
249 chemical contamination from AMLs yielded no comprehensive results. This suggests a notable gap in
250 efforts to consolidate guidance in relation to risk from legacy mine contamination. ~~Addressing this gap
251 would be valuable for developing more universally applicable frameworks and informing risk based
252 decision making in diverse contexts.~~ A SEM can help synthesise current methods, and highlight where
253 guidance is lacking, and how current practice deviates from established guidance.

254 ~~This SEM~~ aims to provide a foundational tool for improving AML-specific risk assessments and
255 guiding future research, policy, and remediation efforts. Consolidating key insights, it seeks to provide
256 a valuable reference for organisations, policymakers, researchers, and practitioners involved in
257 addressing chemical risks from AMLs.

258 The literature search timeframe ~~will be designed to encompass~~ developments over the past two
259 decades, capturing recent advances in AMLs risk assessment methods.

260

261 1.2 Systematic Evidence Map (SEM)

262 Evidence maps follow transparent and replicable methods, including the formulation of structured
263 research questions, comprehensive and reproducible literature searches, and standardised data
264 extraction procedures (James et al., 2016; Wolffe et al., 2019). This ensures consistency and reliability,
265 making evidence maps particularly valuable for informing environmental policy, prioritising future
266 research, and guiding mitigation strategies (James et al., 2016; Miake-Lye et al., 2016).

267 TheyEvidence maps are used to systematically catalogue and visualise the breadth and characteristics
268 of research in any given field (Miake-Lye et al., 2016). In the context of environmental risk assessment,
269 particularly in complex domains such as chemical contamination from abandoned mines, evidence
270 maps help organise diverse sources of information across geographic regions, contaminant types,
271 pathways, and receptors, amongst others factors (James et al., 2016). Unlike traditional systematic
272 reviews that aim to synthesise outcomes, evidence maps focus on providing a high-level overview of
273 the what evidence existing evidence, its areas of concentration, and where it is concentrated, and where
274 significant gaps exist-(Snilstveit et al., 2016). They do not necessarily include or necessitate a critical
275 appraisal of individual studies, and such a step has not been included in the proposed work.

276 Evidence maps follow transparent and replicable methods, including the formulation of structured
277 research questions, comprehensive and reproducible literature searches, and standardised data
278 extraction procedures (James et al., 2016; Wolffe et al., 2019). This ensures consistency and reliability,
279 making evidence maps particularly valuable for informing environmental policy, prioritising future
280 research, and guiding mitigation strategies (James et al., 2016; Miake-Lye et al., 2016).

281 Evidence maps provide descriptive overviews of existing research but do not conduct analyses of the
282 data (Miake-Lye et al., 2016; James et al., 2016; Wolf et al., 2020).

283

284 1.3 Scope

285 Globally, the most mined minerals by weight~~volume~~ are coal, iron ore, aluminium (bauxite), copper,
286 chromium, zinc, titanium, and lead (Casey, 2018; LePan, 2020; Venditti, 2023) with over 7 billion
287 tonnes of coal (IEA News, 2023) and 17 million tonnes of lead-zinc ~~are~~ mined each year (Venditti,
288 2023). Among these, coal and lead mines are of particular concern due to the significant and well-
289 documented severe health risks, especially those linked to exposure associated with legacy
290 contamination from AMLs (Hughes, 2024b; Li & McDonald-Gillespie, 2020; Sartorius, 2023; USE
291 EPA, 2020). Hence, given their substantial toxic legacies, and the environmental persistence,
292 widespread and the extensive documentation of their health and ecological impacts of their-associated
293 metals, lead-zinc mines are valuable case studies within the broader global context of AMLs
294 contamination (Morgan, 2024; Rouhani et al., 2023; Sartorius, 2023, 2024; Tozsin et al., 2022; Wani et

Commented [1]: by volume or weight? You talk about volume and then give the annual weight of the minerals mined.

Commented [2R1]: Yeah, weight not volume. Thanks for spotting that.

295 al., 2021). Accordingly, this evidence map will focus on methods of assessing risks from abandoned
296 coal and lead-zinc mines as representative examples of AML cases.

297 ~~While metals differ in mobility, oxidation states, bioavailability, and toxicity, Pb/Zn and coal AMLs~~
298 ~~may not fully capture the impacts of other abandoned metal and mineral mines, such as abandoned gold~~
299 ~~mines. As a result, all relevant methods may not be fully captured by focusing on Pb/Zn metals and coal~~
300 ~~mines. For example, because of the complex transformation processes of mercury (Alpers et al., 2005),~~
301 ~~abandoned mercury mines may require specific methods of risk assessment, which our approach would~~
302 ~~miss.~~ This limitation is acknowledged, as reviewing all abandoned minerals/metal mines is impractical
303 due to time and resource constraints. ~~Nonetheless, t~~This protocol has been carefully designed and may
304 be adaptable to other types of AMLs, ~~with a focus on evaluating risk assessment methods rather than~~
305 ~~the results of existing conducting risk assessments of AMLs directly.~~ However, ~~given the varying~~
306 ~~behaviour of potentially toxic elements (PTEs) across environmental media, particularly in terms of~~
307 ~~mobility and bioavailability, it can also be adapted for use in assessing other inorganic contaminants.~~
308 ~~However, W~~hen applying the protocol to different contaminant types, it is important to take into
309 ~~account~~ consider compartment specific processes and exposure pathways, ~~that~~ These factors influence
310 ~~the selection of risk assessment methods both for ecological and human health contexts. Furthermore,~~
311 ~~not all methods may be fully captured by focusing on Pb/Zn metals and coal mines. For example,~~
312 ~~because of the complex transformation processes of mercury (Alpers et al., 2005), such AMLs may~~
313 ~~require specific methods of risk assessment, which may be missed in this context.~~

314
315 This SEM seeks to answer the following question: What are the current methods for evaluating chemical
316 risks from abandoned coal and lead-zinc mines? ~~This has been articulated using~~ To support this, a
317 Population, Intervention, and Outcome (PIO) statement ~~was developed~~ (Table 1).

318 Here, the Population refers to the types of AMLs being assessed, the Intervention refers to the chemical
319 risk assessment methods applied, and the Outcome refers to the types of risks or effects identified as
320 impacting ecological and/or human receptors.

321
322 *Table 1: Population, Intervention, and Outcome (PIO) statement of assessment practices relating to*
323 *chemical risk from Abandoned Mine Lands*

What are the current methods for evaluating chemical risks from abandoned coal and lead-zinc mines?	
Population (types of AMLs)	Abandoned mine lands (mines that are no longer active, have been shut down, closed, forgotten, or have ceased operation).

	Only coal and lead-zinc mines; all other former mining activities are out of scope.
Intervention (methods of chemical risk assessment)	Chemical risk assessment practices; studies must include an evaluation of the chemical risks (comparing exposure levels with a safety threshold). Intermediary interventions include exposure assessment and/or modelling, and risk assessment and characterisation. Studies in which actual effects (realised risks) are monitored are within scope, while studies limited to exposure or hazard assessment or characterisation will not be considered.
Outcome (types of risk and effects identified for ecological and human receptors)	Risks and effects of chemicals associated with AMLs on ecological and human receptors
Time Frame	Peer-reviewed studies or grey literature published between the years 2000 to 2024.

324

325 2.0 Materials and Methods

326 This protocol was developed ~~giving~~with due consideration ~~given~~ to the recommendations of the
327 Conduct of Systematic Reviews in Toxicology and Environmental Health Research (COSTER)
328 (Whaley et al., 2020). Deviations from the COSTER recommendations are documented in the
329 supplementary materials ~~file~~ 2.1. This ~~protocol~~ is reported following the Preferred Reporting Items for
330 Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis Protocols (PRISMA-P) guidelines (Moher et al., 2015;
331 Shamseer et al., 2015). The checklist is provided in the supplementary materials ~~file~~ 2.2 (PRISMA-P
332 Checklist).

333

334 2.1 Eligibility Criteria

335 The PIO statement in Table 1 was used ~~as the starting point to~~ articulate ~~to further develop~~ the
336 eligibility criteria ~~for inclusion in the SEM (Table 2) rather than criteria for conducting a chemical risk~~
337 ~~assessment~~, with the following considerations:

338 Population: The focus is on abandoned coal and lead-zinc mines, as they represent an enduring toxic
339 legacy with significant environmental and public health risks. Studies on other types of mines will be
340 excluded, although the protocol may be adaptable for application to other abandoned mine types.

341 Intervention: [This R](#) refers to the chemical risk assessment methods applied to evaluate risk. Initial pilot
 342 activities revealed that there is a large body of literature documenting chemical contamination in AMLs,
 343 but many studies stop short of conducting a chemical risk assessment. Including these studies, which
 344 primarily focus on analytical methods reporting concentrations of chemical contaminants, would add
 345 little value as they have already been extensively researched and reported over the years, and the effort
 346 required would exceed the resources available for this project. The scope was therefore refined and
 347 limited to studies that report or conduct a chemical risk assessment. Consequently, studies focusing
 348 solely on exposure or hazard assessments will be excluded. However, studies that evaluate actual
 349 impacts or harm, i.e., realised risks due to exposure to toxic chemicals from AMLs will be considered
 350 eligible while not specifically targeted by our search strategy.

351 Outcome: Types of risks and impacts identified for ecological and human receptors. Studies
 352 investigating quantitatively measurable toxicological effects on reproduction, growth, behaviour, or
 353 development on ecological and human receptors at the community, population, or individual level will
 354 be included. Studies focusing on physical injury from engineering failures, hazards due to subsidence,
 355 or structural failures of tailings dams will be excluded. Studies focusing solely on exposure
 356 measurement, contaminant fate, transport, bioavailability, and bioaccumulation.

357 [Study design: this evidence map is concerned with primary studies and](#) ~~as well as~~ reviews and meta-
 358 analyses, will ~~also~~ be excluded.

359 Timeframe: To comprehensively capture advances, applications, and persistent gaps in chemical risk
 360 assessment methods for AMLs, studies published between 2000 and 2024 will be included. This
 361 timeframe reflects a period of significant methodological development across international contexts.

362

363 *Table 2: Eligibility criteria*

Element	Statement	Inclusion	Exclusion
Population (types of AMLs)	Abandoned mine lands	Coal and lead-zinc mines. Abandoned open-pit or surface mines. Abandoned underwater and underground mines	Other types of AMLs, such as mercury and arsenic. Active mines, surface, open pit, underground, or underwater mines undergoing reclamation, rehabilitation,

			remediation, or restoration Other types of activities, such as active or abandoned quarries and smelting sites.
Intervention (Methods of chemical risk assessment)	Chemical risk assessment practices	<p>Process: evaluation of the actual effects or potential impacts due to chemical exposures</p> <p>Agents: organic and inorganic chemicals</p> <p>Exposure via water, sediment, soil, dust, air, biota (including food)</p> <p>Receptors: living organisms (humans and non-humans including micro-organisms, plants, vertebrate and invertebrate animals), and their systems (populations, communities, ecosystems)</p>	<p>Process: Studies focusing on inventory, prioritisation of sites, and chemical contamination without assessing the risk of such contamination.</p> <p>Agents: Studies focusing on nanominerals, macrominerals, microplastics, or organometallics</p> <p>Receptors: studies focusing on environmental media as endpoints without assessing associated risks to humans and non-human organisms.</p>

Outcome (types of risk and effects identified for ecological and human receptors)	Chemical risks and effects on ecological and human receptors	Evaluation of chemical/toxicological risks and impacts on reproduction, growth, behaviour, survival, or development in ecological and human receptors.	Physical injury due to natural or engineering hazards (subsidence), structural failure of tailing dams, hydrogeochemical behaviour, rock-water interaction.
Time Frame	Peer-reviewed studies and grey literature	Studies published between 2000 and 2024	Studies published before the year 2000

364

365 2.2 Information sources

366 The following six bibliographic databases will be searched for peer-reviewed articles using search
367 algorithms adequate for each database:

- 368 ● Web of Science
- 369 ● PubMed
- 370 ● Academic Search Complete and Business Source Premier (via [EBSCOhost](#))
- 371 ● Science-Direct
- 372 ● Scopus

373 In addition, manual searches of grey literature not indexed in the selected databases will be conducted,
374 targeting specific websites of government agencies, institutes, and other platforms, including:

- 375 ● International Council on Mining and Metals (ICMM)
- 376 ● US Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA)
- 377 ● UK Environmental Agency (UK EA)
- 378 ● The International Organization for Standardization (ISO)
- 379 ● Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment (CCME)

380

381 2.3 Search Strategy

382 Pilot searches were conducted to iteratively develop the search strategy, with the assistance of an
383 information specialist (JMP) and insights from other systematic evidence maps related to environmental
384 studies. Initially, we planned to include all types of mines in our mapping. However, after conducting
385 preliminary searches, we realised this approach was unmanageable. We refined our focus to coal and
386 lead-zinc mines. During the piloting phase, we noticed many studies simply reported chemical

387 concentrations without contributing significantly to the research question. As a result, we decided to
388 specify our focus on studies assessing risk.

389 This approach addressed the challenge of identifying manuscripts specifically related to chemical risk
390 assessment methods from AMLs, as ~~unspecific vague~~ terms like "assessment" and "risk" ~~often~~ yielded
391 ~~much~~ irrelevant research. The number of hits for synonyms related to the elements of the PIO statement
392 was recorded and combined using Boolean operators to ensure the search strategy maintained sensitivity
393 while achieving some level of specificity.

394 A general approach is shown in Table 3. This was tested across all listed databases, adjusting ~~the~~ search
395 strings to ensure appropriateness in retrieving relevant literature, except for ScienceDirect, which only
396 supports eight Boolean operators, restricting long, complex search algorithms. Truncation of words was
397 used with care. Proximity searches were run to find combined forms of terms. For example, Web of
398 Science uses the proximity operator NEAR/3 while ~~Scopus~~COPUS's is w/3. A simplified search
399 algorithm was developed for ScienceDirect as follows:

400 *(Abandoned OR inactive) AND (coal OR lead OR zinc) AND Mine AND (Contaminant OR Pollution)*
401 *AND "Risk Assessment"*

402 The use of adequate filters, such as article type and publication year, was also explored and applied.
403 The results from piloting the search strategy, the complete search algorithms for each database, the
404 compiled search strings, and the number of articles retrieved from each database are included in the
405 supplementary materials 2.3 (~~S~~earch strategy). The sensitivity of the search strategy was assessed using
406 a set of relevant articles identified during an initial review of the impacts of abandoned coal and lead-
407 zinc mines. All selected articles were successfully retrieved using Web of Science, while 90% were
408 also captured by Scopus and PubMed. This confirmed that our core search terms ~~w~~ould be effective
409 in retrieving key literature relevant to the evidence mapping.

410
411 The term "historic" was initially omitted from the pilot search. To ensure that relevant articles were not
412 missed, this term was later searched separately in combination with other key terms, as shown below:

413
414 *(Historic) NEAR/3 (Coal OR Lead OR Zinc OR mine* OR exploitation OR site OR land) AND (Pollut**
415 *OR contamin* OR chemical) AND (Risk)*

416
417 Details of this additional pilot search and database-specific retrieval are provided in the supplementary
418 materials 2.3 (~~Search Strategy~~), and a flow diagram of the literature search results is presented in
419 Supplementary materials 2.4 (~~Literature Search Results~~).

420

421 Table 3: *General Search strategy combined with Boolean operators*

S/N	Keywords	Synonym
#1	Abandoned mines	(inactive OR historic OR orphan OR derelict OR forgotten OR disused OR deserted OR abandoned) NEAR/3 (Coal OR Lead OR Zinc OR mine* OR exploitation OR site OR land)
#2	Contamination	Pollut* OR contamin* OR chemical
#3	Risk	Risk
Total	#1 AND #2 AND #3	(inactive OR historic OR orphan OR derelict OR forgotten OR disused OR deserted OR abandoned) NEAR/3 (Coal OR Lead OR Zinc OR mine* OR exploitation OR site OR land) AND (Pollut* OR contamin* OR chemical) AND (Risk)

422

423 2.4 Data management

424 The screening of the literature is ~~being~~ managed using CADIMA, a user-friendly, free online tool
425 established by the Julius Kühn Institute and the Collaboration for Environmental Evidence (Julius
426 Kühn Institut, 2017). The Mendeley Reference Manager (Elsevier, 2013) ~~was~~ used to manage manual
427 searches while Citavi (Swiss Academic Software GmbH, 2024) ~~is~~ used for automatic ~~full-text~~
428 retrieval ~~of full-text when that are~~ accessible.

429

430 2.5 Selection Process/Screening

431 The defined eligibility criteria ~~will be~~ applied to screen the merged list of references retrieved from
432 each literature source after the duplicates have been removed. Screening is carried out in two stages. In
433 the first stage, titles and abstracts are examined for relevance to the formulated question, with studies
434 deemed irrelevant excluded. In the second stage, the full texts of the remaining studies from the first
435 stage will be assessed for inclusion. The reasons for excluding studies at the full-text stage will be
436 documented.

437 CADIMA facilitates a consistency check as a method of piloting the screening stage. Any
438 disagreements between screeners were resolved through discussion, and [agreed outcomes of these](#)
439 [discussions were](#) used to revise and clarify the eligibility criteria and ensure a consensus on their
440 interpretation ~~was reached between all parties~~. The eligibility criteria were applied to 15%
441 ~~(randomised automatically generated)~~ by CADIMA) of the merged reference list at [the titles](#) and abstract
442 levels by two reviewers, OVM and URE, the outcome was [assessed as "poor" by Cadima](#), mainly
443 [because differences between 'included' and 'unclear' decisions for each eligibility criterion at the title-](#)
444 [abstract screening stage are recorded as discrepancies, though they do not materially affect the selection](#)
445 [process. Additionally, due to URE first applied a](#) stricter interpretation of the exclusion criteria, ~~where~~
446 ~~leading to some articles that being should have been rated marked as "excluded" when they should~~
447 ~~have been rated "unclear" were instead marked as "excluded"~~. A common example was when the title
448 or abstract referred to AML without specifying the type of mine. ~~All~~The discrepancies [from this pilot](#)
449 [stage](#) were resolved through discussion.

450 URE will screen the remaining articles independently, with an overlap of ~~2~~40% of retrieved articles
451 screened independently in duplicate by OVM as a quality control step. Any disagreements will be
452 discussed as soon as they arise and resolved by consensus to ensure a consistent interpretation of
453 eligibility criteria and avoid drift. If the rate of discrepancies in inclusion-exclusion decisions
454 ~~becomes~~became too high (>1%), ~~(included vs unclear at title abstract screening stage are also~~
455 ~~highlighted as discrepancies, but this has no material influence on the selection process), this should~~
456 ~~trigger duplicate screening of the literature already screened, this will trigger duplicate screening of~~
457 ~~previously screened literature. (Discrepancies between 'included' and 'unclear' decisions at the title-~~
458 ~~abstract screening stage are also recorded, though they do not materially affect the selection process).~~

459

460 2.6 Data extraction

461 A data extraction template was developed and piloted to ensure consistency in the data extraction
462 process. The pilot extraction was conducted independently by two reviewers, [URE and OVM](#).
463 Discrepancies in the extraction process were resolved through discussion and used to refine the data
464 extraction template and ensure that a consensus understanding of the process was reached. The piloted
465 data extraction sheet is available in supplementary materials 2.5 (Data Extraction Sheet-Pilot 1 ~~&~~ and
466 2). The data will be extracted from all included studies by a single reviewer (URE), and a sample of
467 25% of [the](#) extracted data will be independently checked by OVM. The data extraction ~~sheet~~-template
468 is designed to facilitate identification, documentation, and validation by a second reviewer. The
469 finalised data extraction template is included in supplementary materials 2.6 (Finalised data extraction
470 template). A coding strategy combining both deductive and inductive approaches was developed to
471 guide the data extraction process and is provided in the supplementary materials 2.7 (Code Book for

472 Data Extraction). This dual approach was selected to ensure both consistency and flexibility in capturing
473 relevant information across studies. The deductive component involved the predefined categorisation
474 of commonly encountered data types to standardise data recording. In parallel, the inductive component
475 was designed to allow for the identification and categorisation of emerging terms or concepts, ~~both prior~~
476 ~~to and~~ during the extraction process.

477 In brief, the following data will be extracted from all studies included during the full-text screening
478 stage:

- 479 ● Bibliographic meta-data: Author(s), year, journal name, journal details (volume, issue, page),
480 article title and abstract, and source of funding.
- 481 ● Abandoned mined land details: study location (country, state, or county where the study was
482 carried out), mine name, information about the type of mine, method of mining, duration of
483 operation, and year of abandonment).
- 484 ● Exposure measurement (if relevant): Sample medium, sampling strategy, sample storage, and
485 preparation, sample volume (unit), method of chemical analysis, the limit of detection
486 (including unit), precision, accuracy, contaminant or pollutant name, CAS number,
487 information about the reported concentrations including the unit in the article, and other
488 contextual measurements.
- 489 ● Exposure modelling (if relevant): Source medium, pathway, target media, modelling method,
490 and reference used to model the exposure, chemical name, CAS number, and outcome.
- 491 ● Effect monitoring (if relevant): Taxonomic group, species, sampling strategy/method, sample
492 storage and preparation, sample size (unit), type and level of observed effect, measurement
493 methods, statistically significant, statistical methods, reported outcomes.
- 494 ● Risk characterisation: source, exposure pathway, receptor, risk characterisation method,
495 reference for the method used, the source of reference dose used (~~as well as notes on the~~
496 ~~selection of the reference dose when this is reported~~), uncertainty factors, risk category,
497 outcome, consideration of mixtures.

498 This data extraction process is designed to systematically capture key components relevant to chemical
499 risk assessment at AMLs. ~~This approach is structured to ensure that all necessary information is~~
500 ~~included to assess risk accurately and comprehensively.~~

501 First, bibliographic metadata will be extracted to organise ~~and classify~~ the studies included in this
502 evidence map. This information helps establish the context ~~for the conduct~~ of each study, including its
503 authorship, source of funding, publication details, abstract, and ~~doi/DOI, which are essential for~~
504 ~~understanding the scope of the research and its applicability to the overall mapping process.~~

505 The details of the abandoned mine lands, such as the location, type of mine, mining method, and
506 duration of abandonment, are crucial for evaluating environmental impacts. These factors influence the

507 pollution pathways and long-term risks associated with AMLs. Information about the mining history,
508 waste characteristics, and local geology is fundamental to predicting and assessing site-specific
509 environmental risks. The data from this section will help evaluate the applicability of different risk
510 assessment methods across specific contexts and support subset analyses of methodological differences.

511 Exposure assessment methods include details on the sampling strategy, storage and preparation of
512 samples, and the chemical analysis techniques used. Parameters such as the medium of exposure,
513 contaminant(s), and limit of detection data will help inform the applicability and performance of the
514 methods described. Exposure modelling is often essential for extrapolating measured concentrations of
515 contaminants in environmental media to concentrations in relevant pathways of exposure. Information
516 such as the exposure pathways, target media, and modelling methods helps to document current
517 methods used to predict human and ecological receptor exposure to chemical contaminants from AMLs.

518 Effect monitoring data, such as the taxonomic group, species involved, and the type and level of effects
519 observed, provide crucial evidence of the actual risks faced by receptors exposed to AML contaminants.
520 These data are particularly important for identifying realised risks and understanding the ecological and
521 human health consequences of chemical exposure. ~~These data can be used to compare realised observed~~
522 ~~risks with those predicted by chemical risk assessments.~~

523 Finally, data from risk characterisation methods, including references to the guidelines or method used,
524 and the incorporation of uncertainty factors, will help document the range of risk assessment methods
525 and applications across various exposure sources and routes. Also, information on whether mixture
526 risks are considered, along with the range of methods used, will be recorded.

527 The extraction of these data types will ensure that the evidence map captures a comprehensive overview
528 of current practices, which will allow us to query and document advancements, applications, and any
529 gaps in methods related to risk from AMLs. Piloting the data extraction has helped to establish
530 guidelines for maintaining a consistent format to extract data from included studies. The use of drop-
531 down menus also allows for categorisation, which will facilitate the data analysis. Following the
532 extraction process, the data will be cleaned, such as removing irrelevant symbols, units, or numbers,
533 before analysis ~~and revisiting~~ ~~revisiting~~ categorisation, as appropriate.

534

535 2.7 Data analysis and reporting

536 The outcome will address our objectives: identifying procedures, extracting relevant information for
537 evaluating chemical risks, and establishing current best practices related to chemical risk assessment of
538 AMLs.

539 The key characteristics of ~~abandoned~~ mines that have undergone risk assessment will be summarised
540 in tabular format, accompanied by a map visualising their geographic locations. Information related to

541 exposure measurement, exposure modelling, effect monitoring, and risk characterisation will also be
542 summarised in tables. This analysis aims to provide insights into both the diversity and frequency of
543 various methodologies and practices used to characterise chemical risks from AMLs. This will be
544 complemented by a critical narrative ~~critical~~ synthesis of the elements ~~what~~ researchers ~~deemed~~
545 identified as necessary in the included studies.

546 The visualisation software Tableau (Salesforce Inc, 2025) allows for the creation of interactive
547 dashboards, enabling users to select subsets of data and easily view all relevant references and sources
548 of information. Tableau will be employed to illustrate quantitatively the use of categories of methods
549 data sets from each risk assessment step~~process~~ category and generate reports that summarise findings,
550 highlighting key insights.

551
552 We will address the “current method” question for each risk assessment step~~of the four categories~~
553 through narrative analysis and trend evaluation from the database. Tableau will help track changes over
554 time, illustrating how method evidence has evolved. This will be compared with Part of this process
555 will involve reviewing the methods used, compiling a list to determine which methods are considered
556 current, and establishing criteria for this distinction. Additionally, we will examine guidance documents
557 from organisations such as the US EPA, UK EA, ICM, and ISO ~~to understand the recommended~~
558 approaches for risk characterisation related to AMLs. The collated methods will be compared with
559 currently available guidance to assess alignment and deviations. Through the data analysis, we aim to
560 identify scientific advancements in risk-AML chemical risk assessment methods~~characterisation within~~
561 the study timeframe and highlight improvements made over recent~~the~~ years. Identified gaps and
562 limitations will also be documented.

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